

Forecasting indoor air temperatures in tropical hospitals to improve patient health and preparedness for extreme heat

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ABSTRACT

Extreme heat is a growing public health threat in tropical Africa, especially in Ghana where outdoor maximum daily temperatures (Tx) regularly exceed 35 °C. Vulnerability to heat is socially and economically differentiated, with pregnant women, young children, elderly people, and people with chronic health conditions most at risk. High proportions of these groups are found in hospitals, yet little is known about extreme temperatures inside wards. This paper addresses these gaps by developing proof-of-concept forecasting models for indoor air temperatures in Ghanaian hospital wards. A significant contribution of this work is the novel, high-resolution, empirical indoor environment dataset collected from four hospitals capturing a variety of building types in two distinct climate zones. This dataset enabled the development and testing of heat-health early warning systems which significantly contributes to a scalable, generalisable framework for climate adaptation in healthcare buildings across the tropical Global South. Measured indoor Tx were statistically related to numerical weather predictions of outdoor temperatures to create models capable of explaining up to 75% of the variance in daily Tx with accuracies of ~1 °C at 24 h forecasting times. Such heat alerts could be used by hospital authorities to adjust staffing levels for expected surges in patient volumes, and for rescheduling of elective non-urgent outpatient treatments to free up capacity during heatwaves. We assert, however, that heat-health early warning systems should be integrated alongside other measures to adapt to rising indoor temperatures, such as improving hospital design, formulating heat-health action plans, and raising awareness of heat-related health issues.

1. Introduction

Extreme heat causes 4.6 million premature deaths annually [1] – a level of heat-related mortality that is expected to rise under climate change [2]. People living in tropical Africa are at particular risk of adverse health effects as temperatures already hover close to the lethal threshold year-round [3]. Furthermore, the likelihood of very high temperatures is exacerbated by rapid growth of cities and consequent intensification of the urban heat island (UHI) [4,5]. Empirical evidence suggests that an UHI can increase local temperatures by 0.3 to 0.5 °C per million people in a city [6]. To date, the vast majority of studies have focused on changes in the frequency and intensity of urban heat for

outdoor environments; relatively little attention has been given to how regional climate change, combined with urban growth, building forms and use, may contribute to rising extreme indoor temperatures. Moreover, extreme heat and health impact research under-represent the most at-risk populations in the Global South [7,8].

Overheating of indoor spaces is already a serious concern for low-income urban communities across Africa [9–15]. However, exposure and sensitivity to high indoor temperatures is socially and economically differentiated. The most vulnerable include the elderly (particularly those who are dehydrated) [16], the very young [17], pregnant women and their unborn babies [18], outdoor workers and people with chronic health conditions [19]. During hot weather, heat-related hospital

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admissions increase especially amongst vulnerable groups [20,21]. Yet, evidence from hospitals in low-income urban areas shows these facilities may not provide respite from heat and may even become so overheated that they exacerbate existing patient health conditions [22,23].

Hospitals are critical facilities where patients should receive protection from extreme heat. Unfortunately, this is not always the case, and some groups are at particularly high risk. For example, heat exposure in the last week of pregnancy is associated with increased stillbirths and longer labour [24]. Sweating can cause wound infections [22]. The elderly, who comprise a large proportion of inpatients, are physiologically less able to cope with high temperatures [25]. People on certain medications are at increased risk of dying during heatwaves too [26]. Hence, it is imperative that hospitals are prepared for high indoor temperatures so they can protect their vulnerable patients.

One way of reducing risks to patients could be to implement heat-health early warning systems (HEWS). These can give administrators advance notice of extreme heat events and surges in heat-related hospital admissions. With sufficient warning, it may be possible to bolster staff rosters, set up temporary cooling systems, postpone elective non-urgent outpatient treatments, or even relocate the most at-risk patients to cooler spaces. Such preparations can help to free-up staff and ward capacities to handle more admissions. Accordingly, the World Meteorological Organization and World Health Organization have long regarded HEWS as an important part of heat risk adaptation [27]. Despite their potential, prior studies highlight a lack of human-centred and meteorological data from low- and middle-income countries with which to develop and test HEWS [28]. Data for indoor temperatures in hospitals and health centres is even harder to obtain, yet is essential for building ward-level, heat forecasts. Such information could supplement more conventional outdoor heat forecasts issued by state meteorological agencies.

The aim of our research is to address these gaps by developing a proof-of-concept forecasting model to predict indoor air temperatures in tropical hospital wards. This represents the first ward-level indoor temperature forecasting system for tropical African hospitals with 24-month empirical validation. This was achieved by statistically relating high-resolution measurements of indoor temperature in four hospitals in Ghana to gridded re-analysis or numerical weather predictions of outdoor temperatures. Ghana was selected because of its high temperature exposure, data accessibility through established research partnerships, and hospital cooperation in facilitating long-term monitoring. Our resulting algorithms are used to evaluate the local conditions under which a skilful operational HEWS might eventually be deployed. Statistical models of indoor temperatures have been developed previously for homes and workplaces in the Global North (e.g., [29]). As far as we are aware, we are the first to advance such techniques for hospitals globally.

2. Data and study sites

2.1. Data sources

This study is based on three datasets: (1) dry bulb (air) temperatures from sensors sited at various indoor and outdoor locations in selected hospital wards; (2) European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts ERA5 air temperatures¹; and (3) National Centers for Environmental Prediction Global Forecast System (GFS) air temperatures.²

In situ air temperatures were recorded over a 24-month period from 1 July 2022 to 1 July 2024 in the cities of Accra and Tamale, Ghana. However, eight days were removed from the statistical analysis because of missing data in the GFS reanalysis (due to data quality issues in the

dataset during these specific dates). These days were 28 October 2023, 13 and 26 December 2023, 21 February 2024, 7 and 8 March 2024, and 20 and 29 May 2024.

Indoor and outdoor dry bulb (air) temperature was measured at 15-minute intervals by Eltek MS47B sensors,³ which log recorded data to the internal memory of each device (with accuracy ± 0.4 °C). Sensors were calibrated by the manufacturer one month prior to installation. No post-deployment calibration was performed during the 24-month monitoring period; however, sensor performance was verified through cross-comparisons with outdoor measurements and ERA5 reanalysis data to detect potential drift or failure. Indoor sensors were mounted on walls at a height of 1.6 to 2.2 m, away from direct solar radiation and draughts from windows and doors. A sensor was placed inside each ward of interest. Initially, one sensor per hospital was situated outdoors, away from direct solar radiation, rain, and external air-conditioning units. However, one of the sensors in Accra was tampered with, and another in Tamale was subsequently found to be affected by late afternoon sun at certain times of the year. Therefore, one sensor was used to represent outdoor temperatures on hospital grounds in Accra (5.545 N, -0.213 E), and another in Tamale (9.393 N, -0.823 E).

ERA5-Land air temperature data (~ 9 km resolution) were extracted for the grid-points closest to hospitals and at 2 m to match sensor locations and height above the ground. ERA5 data were retrieved from the C3S Climate Data Store using the *cdsapip* Python package (v0.5.1). ERA5 data were then post-processed to obtain temperatures at 00:00, 06:00, 12:00, and 18:00, to correspond with the GFS output times (see Section 3). These four values were used to specify the daily maximum (T_x) and minimum (T_n), as well as to calculate the daily mean (T_m) temperature. These ERA5 data were used to benchmark the skill of downscaling site-specific indoor and outdoor temperatures from concurrent, large-scale (gridded) air temperatures.

GFS air temperature data (~ 28 km resolution) were obtained via a custom data request form and downloaded from the website, then processed using Python. Again, these data were extracted for the grid-points closest to hospitals. GFS temperature forecasts are issued four times per day at 00:00, 06:00, 12:00, and 18:00, with lead times extending up to 384 h (16 days). Here, we use only forecasts that are 24 h ahead to demonstrate proof-of-concept. As with ERA5, we took the T_x and T_n from the four available forecasts, regardless of the time of day. However, we concentrated our analyses on forecasts of T_x given the potential threat to inpatient health and comfort.

2.2. Study sites

Measurements of indoor and outdoor temperatures took place in four hospitals in Ghana, West Africa (Fig. 1). Ghana was chosen because the country experiences 80–100 days per year with outdoor daily T_x exceeding 35 °C [15,30]. Of the four hospitals studied, two are located in the southern capital of Accra and two in the northern city of Tamale. The climate of Accra is coastal savannah with local mean daily T_x ranging from 28 °C in July–September (the rainy season) to 33 °C in March (the peak of the dry season). The climate of Tamale is tropical wet and dry with a range of mean daily T_x from 30 °C in July–September to 38 °C in March [11]. Extreme heat is recognised as an escalating public health threat, especially in the northern parts of Ghana [31].

In Accra, five hospital wards and one outdoor sensor were used for analysis; similarly, in Tamale five indoor and one outdoor sensor were installed. All wards had windows for natural ventilation provision, but assumptions were made about their frequency and duration of use based on conversations with staff. Some wards also had mechanical ventilation and a small number had air-conditioning (Table 1). Wards were deliberately selected with inpatients that are particularly vulnerable to

¹ <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-land?tab=overview>

² <https://rda.ucar.edu/datasets/ds084.1/>

³ These devices also collected relative humidity and carbon dioxide concentration data, but these were not used in this study.

Fig. 1. Location of study areas of Accra and Tamale, Ghana. Source: Gough et al. [12].

extreme heat, namely, those for pregnant women, premature babies, infants (under 6 months age), and children. Ethical clearance was provided by the hospital authorities to work in these environments. In order to protect patient and ward confidentiality, all spaces monitored were codified and numbered (A-site ward codes for Accra, and T-site ward codes for Tamale).

2.3. Methods

Scatter plots were first used to visualise associations between recorded indoor Tx (the dependent variable) in each ward compared with outdoor Tx from observations, ERA5, or GFS (the independent variables). These preliminary analyses were undertaken to identify

Table 1

Accra (A) and Tamale (T) hospital wards monitored, ward code, patients, ward dimensions, natural ventilation type, presence of mechanical ventilation, and presence of air-conditioning (A/C), height of sensor from floor.

Hospital number	Space monitored	Ward code	Patients	Floor area (m ²)	Ward volume (m ³)	Natural ventilation	Mech. vent.	Cooling	Sensor height (m)
A1	Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU)	06582	Neonatal (premature unstable)	23	75	Sliding panes	No	Ductless A/C	1.6
A1	Emergency	06591	Children	45	125	Sliding panes	No	Ductless A/C	1.6
A2	External	06593	-	-	-	-	-	Outdoors	1.6
A2	Emergency	06602	All	36	97	Adjustable louvres	No	No	1.6
A2	Maternity	06603	Pregnant women	20.5	55	Adjustable louvres	No	No	1.6
A2	Paediatrics	06605	Children	18	52	Adjustable louvres	No	No	1.6
T1	Paediatrics U6m	06578	Children under 6 months	34	112	Adjustable and fixed open louvres	No	Ductless A/C	1.6
T1	External	06587	-	-	-	-	-	Outdoors	2.2
T1	Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU)	06588	Neonatal (premature unstable)	33	89	Sliding panes	Yes	Ducted A/C	2.2
T1	Pre-natal	06579	Pregnant women	46	152	Adjustable and fixed open louvres	Yes	No	1.6
T2	Maternity	06608	Pregnant women and stable neonates	106	382	Side-hung casement	No	No	1.6
T2	Male	06609	Adult males	114	378	Adjustable and fixed open louvres	No	No	1.6

wards with potential outdoor-indoor temperature predictability. We hypothesised that such relationships would be strongest in wards *without* the confounding impact of air-conditioning. To reflect local conditions, separate linear regression models of daily indoor Tx were built for each ward. These models were benchmarked against a Zero Order Forecast (ZOF) which simply assumes that the temperature tomorrow is the same as the temperature observed today – in other words a lag-1 day persistence model [32]. More sophisticated machine learning or autoregressive techniques could have been used (e.g., [29,33]), but we begin by developing parsimonious linear and ZOF models.

Two methods were used to calibrate and test the linear regressions of outdoor-indoor air temperatures against data not used in model creation:

- 1) **Resampling cross-validation:** Indoor temperature data for wards were linearly regressed separately against recorded outdoor temperatures, ERA5, or GFS. Individual models were fit to a random sample of 90 % of the days, with the remaining 10 % used to evaluate model predictions. The 90/10 split was chosen to maximize training data while retaining sufficient validation samples (approximately 73 days) for robust error estimation. Sampling was performed randomly without stratification to reflect operational forecast conditions. The amount of explained variance (r^2) and the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) was calculated for each model variant. This process was repeated 1000 times, in order to build up a distribution of r^2 and MAE values based on the model skill at predicting the unseen data. Separate models were built for Tx, Tm, and Tn giving 90,000 variants in total (i.e., 3 temperature series x 3 independent variables x 10 sites x 1000 samples).
- 2) **Split-record validation:** The first half of each 2-year indoor temperature series was fit by linear regression to outdoor temperatures (from observations, ERA5, or GFS). Recorded indoor temperatures from the second half of the series were then predicted by each of the three models. In step two, the second half of the series was used to fit the models and the first period for testing predicted values. In step 3, the predicted series from the first and second halves were concatenated. This gives three complete time-series of model predictions to compare with observed indoor series not used in model calibration. This procedure was applied to Tx, Tm, and Tn giving 90 regression models in total (i.e., 3 temperature indices x 3 independent variables x 10 sites).

Note that *concurrent* outdoor Tx (from observations or ERA5) or 24 h

forecast Tx (from GFS) were used to fit regression models of indoor Tx. The former reveals the upper bound of model accuracy that might be expected given best available site or gridded information about outdoor temperatures. The latter demonstrates the potential skill of predicting future ward Tx from outdoor temperatures forecasted 24 h in advance. Hence, models based on GFS assimilate uncertainties from indoor measurements, outdoor temperature forecasts, and regression model parameters. By comparing outdoor Tx from observations with concurrent outdoor Tx from ERA5 and GFS, we are able to quantify local biases in the latter inputs to the regression models. However, it was not possible to build multivariate regression models with other variables (such as solar radiation and rainfall) as we did not have such observations at the hospital sites.

As well as the ability to simulate observed Tx, we are also interested in the capacity of each model to issue indoor heat warnings for the next 24 h. Using a Tx threshold of 32 °C (90 °F), we convert the observed and forecasted temperatures into series of 0 s (equal to or below the threshold) and 1 s (above the threshold). In healthcare settings, morbidity was found to increase above 32 °C [34]. Furthermore, this is the temperature around which fans running at moderate velocities and relative humidities are no longer effective at cooling the human body [35]. This threshold aligns with thermal comfort research in tropical climates and provides a practical benchmark for operational heat warnings, though local health authorities may wish to adjust this based on ward-specific patient vulnerabilities. For example, maternity delivery rooms may require warmer temperatures [36], but evidence is rare (especially in a tropical climate setting) and often contradictory [34]. Other specific physiological vulnerabilities related to ambient temperature for high-risk pre-term neonates are likely to be managed by incubators in most healthcare settings [37], and so ward temperature is less influential on health outcomes. It is also noted that other hospital occupants (staff and visitors) require different conditions for comfort than patients [38]. The 32 °C temperature threshold is therefore applied with acknowledgement that vulnerability of hospital occupants to temperature is heterogeneous, but that is sensible given the current research evidence. In light of this, the sensitivity of forecast skill to the choice of the threshold temperature was also tested, by deriving TSS (Eq. (1)) in the range 32 ± 1 °C. A wider extent was not possible as some wards had maximum Tx less than 34 °C.

Following Sulzer et al. [29], we used the true skill score (TSS) to evaluate forecasts:

$$TSS = \left(\frac{a}{a+c} \right) - \left(\frac{b}{b+d} \right) \tag{Eq. 1}$$

where *a* is a “hit” when both the observation and forecast exceed the

threshold; *b* is a “false alarm” when only the forecast exceeds the threshold; *c* is a “miss” when the observation exceeds the threshold, but the forecast does not; and *d* is a “correct rejection” when neither the observation nor the forecast exceeds the threshold.

Fig. 2. Outdoor-indoor relationships for daily maximum air temperatures (Tx) in five hospital wards in Accra compared with outdoor Tx observed by sensor “ID_06593”, concurrent ERA5 and 24 h ahead GFS, during the period July 2022 to July 2024.

Fig. 3. Outdoor-indoor relationships for daily maximum air temperatures (Tx) in five hospital wards in Tamale compared with the outdoor Tx observed by sensor “ID_06587”, concurrent ERA5 and 24 h ahead GFS, during the period July 2022 to July 2024.

3. Results

3.1. Associations between outdoor-indoor temperatures in different wards

Our analyses evaluated the extent to which concurrent outdoor temperatures from a) the hospital site or b) from gridded data (ERA5 or GFS) correlate with recorded indoor temperatures. To maximise the value of information for managing inpatient health, we focus on associations with indoor Tx in the five hospital wards of Accra (Fig. 2) and the five of Tamale (Fig. 3). Comparable plots are provided for daily Tm and Tn in the **Supplementary Information (Figures S1 and S2)**.

The data show that observed outdoor Tx is consistently higher than gridded outdoor Tx from ERA5 and GFS, with the latter having a greater cool bias, especially in Accra. The mean cool bias was approximately 1.5 °C for GFS and 0.8 °C for ERA5 compared to observed outdoor temperatures in Accra, and 1.2 °C for GFS and 0.5 °C for ERA5 in Tamale. As expected, Tx inside wards with air-conditioning behaves independently of outdoor Tx as evidenced by the low r^2 even for observed outdoor data (see Accra sites 06582 and 06591 in Fig. 2; and for Tamale sites 06578 and 06588 in Fig. 3). Conversely, Tx in wards with natural ventilation have much stronger associations with observed outdoor Tx as shown by the higher r^2 values, which range between 0.64 – 0.68 for Accra (in wards 06602, 06603, 06605), and 0.81 – 0.92 for Tamale (in wards 06589, 06608, 06609).

Overall, the strongest associations between concurrent outdoor-indoor Tx were obtained from both ERA5 and GFS ($r^2 = 0.72$) in Accra for a ward designated as an emergency treatment room (06602). In Tamale, the strongest correlations were between observed outdoor-indoor Tx ($r^2 = 0.92$) for stable neonate (06608) and male inpatient (06609) wards. We speculate that the stronger correlations in Tamale are due to greater natural ventilation of wards and hence connectivity to outdoor conditions. This is supported by the ventilation characteristics shown in Table 1, where all naturally ventilated Tamale wards utilise adjustable louvres that facilitate continuous air exchange with outdoor conditions.

3.2. Forecasting indoor Tx for naturally ventilated wards

The 24 h forecast skill of the GFS linear regression and ZOF models was evaluated using the r^2 , MAE, and TSS metrics for six naturally ventilated wards. The following results are based on the resampling and split-record validation. The former shows expected but only modest increases in MAE when comparing concurrent (ERA5) with forecasted (GFS) indoor Tx (Fig. 4; see Figure S4 for r^2 distributions). For most wards in Tamale, the modal MAE increases by ~0.25 °C for GFS compared with ERA5. In Accra, the distributions of MAE for GFS and ERA5 generally overlap for indoor Tx, signalling little or no increase in errors for the 24 h ahead forecasts. Moreover, the errors for concurrent and forecasted indoor Tx are generally lower than for outdoor Tx.

In Accra, the split-record r^2 for GFS ranged between 0.57 to 0.65, and for ZOF between 0.75 to 0.90 (Table 2). The majority of models had MAE less than 1 °C. Overall, the TSS at 32 °C was higher for the ZOF model than for GFS due to a greater number of hits and fewer missed heat alerts. Sensitivity testing revealed lower TSS at higher thresholds for both ZOF and GFS models. Time-series plots show that concurrent (downscaled ERA5) and forecast (GFS) models better capture extreme Tx for indoors than for outdoors (sensor 06593) (Fig. 5; see Figure S5 for plots of Tm). This is because the day-to-day variance in observed Tx is more damped indoors. Even so, both ERA5 and GFS tend to underestimate observed Tx in wards during the relatively hot winter of 2023/24.

In Tamale, the split-record r^2 for GFS ranged between 0.60 to 0.75, and for ZOF between 0.74 to 0.85 (Table 2). All models had MAE less than or equal to 1 °C. Again, the TSS was marginally higher for the ZOF (0.62 to 0.79) than for GFS (0.60 to 0.75) models, in this case due to fewer false alarms and more correct rejections. Forecast skill (TSS) was also better at the higher threshold (33 °C) when the combined number of

hits (a) and misses (c) was greater than 100 days. The time-series show strong agreement between observed, ERA5 and GFS estimates of both outdoor (sensor 06587) and indoor daily Tx (Fig. 6).

The ZOF model is more skilful than the GFS model for the majority of the unventilated wards, except for a paediatric ward in Accra (06,605) and maternity ward in Tamale (06608) (Fig. 7). In these cases, GFS provides more reliable 24 h ahead heat alerts for days with Tx > 32 °C. Nonetheless, outliers in the scatterplots suggest that both models struggle with extreme heat onset (forecast Tx too low) and termination (forecast Tx too high). This suggests that other predictor variables – such as solar radiation or rainfall – may be needed alongside outdoor Tx to capture such rapid transitions in temperature.

4. Discussion

4.1. Forecast skill and outputs

The results of our testing suggest that daily maximum temperatures (Tx) can be forecasted inside naturally ventilated wards in Accra and Tamale at 24 h lead times with accuracies of ~1 °C. In some wards, the GFS-based model was able to explain up to 75 % of the variance in daily Tx. Our TSS values were also comparable to results obtained from more elaborate and data-intensive, machine learning models (e.g., [29]). Our models were calibrated using just two years of data gathered by low-cost sensors installed in hospital wards. Hence, they represent a parsimonious point of departure that can be used to benchmark more sophisticated models in future.

Despite being the simplest possible model, the ZOF was generally more skilful at predicting indoor Tx and heat alerts than GFS. This arises from the fact that day-to-day Tx are highly autocorrelated due to the thermal inertia of buildings. In other words, the Tx of today provides a very good first order estimate of the Tx tomorrow. However, the ZOF would require continuous real-time monitoring of indoor temperatures in order to be operationalised within a bespoke tropical hospital HEWS. Further research is needed to compare the relative skill of the ZOF and GFS over longer forecast horizons than 24 h ahead. The GFS model – once calibrated for in situ ward conditions – can be run automatically without the need for continuous monitoring. But the accuracy of the indoor 24 h forecasts derived from GFS depend on the errors in the outdoor forecasts of Tx. A comparison of the amounts of explained variance (r^2) in indoor Tx by GFS with the “perfect” forecasts of ERA5 shows the extent of these errors. The r^2 for ERA5 were always equal to or greater than those for GFS (Figs. 2 and 3).

Both the ZOF and GFS models struggled to replicate abrupt temperature changes observed at the beginning and end of the hot seasons in 2024 – especially for wards in Accra. This may be attributed to lack of information about building heat gains from intense solar radiation during the dry season [39], or evaporative cooling from rainfall at the start of the wet season [40]. These shortcomings could be addressed by assimilating solar radiation and rainfall forecasts from GFS, alongside temperature, in the next generation of our indoor Tx model. Among additional predictor variables, it is anticipated that solar radiation would have the greatest impact on forecast skill during dry season heat events, followed by rainfall during transitional periods. Other explanatory meteorological variables such as wind speed, atmospheric humidity, and pressure might also be included in a multivariate statistical model, but it is expected these would offer only marginal improvements. Likewise, information about ward occupancy levels and ventilation systems might also be incorporated. Model outputs could be extended to cover wet-bulb temperatures (i.e., humid heat), or other bioclimatic heat indices that reflect heat exchanges between the environment and people [31,41]. Likewise, where observations are available, statistical models could be developed to forecast air quality in wards and/or energy consumption (for air-conditioning) in hospitals and nursing homes [42].

To the author’s knowledge, this is the first study of its kind to develop

Fig. 4. Mean Absolute Error (MAE) in concurrent daily Tx outdoors (top row) and indoors (other rows) predicted by ERA5 (blue bars) and 24 h ahead for GFS (red bars) based on 1000 cross-validations for Accra (left) and Tamale (right).

Table 2

Skill of 24 h forecasts of indoor Tx by the GFS and ZOF models for naturally ventilated wards in Accra and Tamale. The main threshold used for TSS was $32\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Wards	GFS			ZOF						
	r^2	MAE ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	TSS			r^2	MAE ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	TSS		
			31 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	32 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	33 $^{\circ}\text{C}$			31 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	32 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	33 $^{\circ}\text{C}$
Accra code										
06602	0.65	0.8	0.79	0.51	0.28	0.90	0.4	0.82	0.72	0.60
06603	0.64	0.8	0.57	0.15	0.00	0.90	0.4	0.79	0.68	0.24
06605	0.57	1.2	0.66	0.75	0.54	0.75	0.9	0.78	0.78	0.57
Tamale code										
06579	0.60	1.0	0.66	0.61	0.46	0.85	0.6	0.83	0.78	0.71
06608	0.73	0.9	0.42	0.69	0.76	0.74	0.9	0.54	0.62	0.78
06609	0.75	0.9	0.46	0.67	0.74	0.84	0.7	0.64	0.79	0.80

Fig. 5. Observed daily maximum temperatures (Tx) compared with ERA5 (concurrent) and GFS (24 h ahead) for naturally ventilated wards in Accra.

and evaluate indoor temperature forecasting models for the purpose of heatwave early warning systems in healthcare buildings. We advance the field by demonstrating the predictive skill of these forecasting models in complex hospital environments. Previous research tended to focus on domestic (e.g., [43]) or office buildings [29,44]. Others focus on population-level risks [45] or hospital admissions, rather than the conditions once inside the hospital [46]. The present study, however, demonstrates temperature forecasting performance in large, densely-occupied healthcare buildings with a variety of interacting ventilation systems, and occupants who are vulnerable to the negative

health effects of extreme heat.

4.2. Improving preparedness for indoor extreme heat

The ultimate goal of HEWS is to reduce mortality and morbidity through improved preparedness for dangerous (indoor) heat. Ideally, forecast outputs and thresholds would be customised to meet the needs of local decision makers and vulnerable populations. We mainly focused on a heat alert threshold of indoor daily Tx > 32 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for illustrative purposes – but these forecast variable(s) and threshold(s) could be

Fig. 6. Observed daily maximum temperatures (Tx) compared with ERA5 (concurrent) and GFS (24 h ahead) for predominantly naturally ventilated wards in Tamale.

adjusted on a ward-by-ward basis to give better patient-centred warnings. For example, a 24-hour forecast predicting indoor Tx exceeding 32 °C in a maternity ward would enable staff to pre-position fans, ensure adequate hydration supplies for patients, adjust delivery scheduling where possible, and increase nursing staff ratios to monitor for heat-related complications in mothers and neonates. Moreover, our sensitivity testing showed that forecast skill (TSS) depends on the threshold – underlining the case for setting ward-specific values that reflect patient needs.

Forecasts could also provide valuable information about the working environments of carers, which can directly impact their well-being and productivity. Hospital managers and staff should be consulted about the most meaningful forecast outputs, alert thresholds, and lead-times when devising forecasting systems to support operational decision-making before extreme heat events. This could cover amendments to staffing levels, rescheduling of elective non-urgent outpatient treatments, or distribution of temporary cooling equipment to wards without air-conditioning. From an operational perspective, implementing these forecasting tools would require minimal infrastructure: an internet connection to access weather forecasts, basic computing capacity to run regression models, and a communication system to disseminate heat-health alerts to hospitals and ward managers. An indoor temperature sensor network would also be required to initially train and test the

models but once calibrated indoor temperature forecasts can be automatically generated without further sensing, and so these devices could be removed and installed in another hospital. Installation, calibration, and redeployment of a single set of sensors around several hospitals would be a cost-effective solution.

This study suggests that a 12-month calibration period is sufficient. This does, however, assume that consistent ventilation behaviours continue beyond the initial calibration period. Evidence from hospitals is rare, but a study of two hospitals in China suggests that indoor air temperature drives window opening behaviours with broader seasonal differences also occurring [47], which is corroborated by the more widely researched domestic environment [48]. No evidence exists for the climate region of the present study, however. Nonetheless, a 12-month calibration period would capture these seasonal differences. Where there would be possible issues is if a new staff member was introduced to the ward who implemented different window operation regimes, or a permanent change in guidance, such as in response to new advice around air quality [49], then the models may no longer be applicable to that ward and a new calibration dataset would be required. Similarly, if a ward switches from being naturally ventilated to mechanically ventilated (with or without cooling) then the indoor temperature forecasts would also become unreliable.

A key strength of the study is its potential for generalisability across

Fig. 7. Comparison of 24 h forecasts with observations of indoor daily Tx for a paediatric ward in Accra (06605) and maternity ward in Tamale (06,608), using the GFS and ZOF models.

the tropics, which is home to almost half the world's population – extending the work's reach and impact. Firstly, the modelling framework was calibrated using two different tropical climate zones - Guinea Savanna and Coastal Savanna [50]. The use of two climate zones gives confidence that the model is robust under varying local and seasonal sub-climates, suggesting it could be reliably applied across other tropical regions which are likely to be driven by the same climate input variables. Secondly, the study monitored a range of hospital types - two built in the early 1900s and two built after 1970 (one of each age category per climate zone). This demonstrates that the modelling framework can operate independently of hospital construction age, materials, and design, which increases the confidence that this modelling framework can be generalised more widely. Thirdly, the models worked in both the higher-density urban environment of Accra, and also in the lower-density environment of Tamale where sheltering by surrounding buildings was limited. Consequently, the modelling framework is likely to be generalisable across the climate region in a variety of hospital types, providing the wards are naturally-ventilated. As natural ventilation is the primary cooling strategy for many healthcare facilities in low-resource settings [49,51,52], this work is highly relevant in places least able to adapt to a warming climate. Despite the above possibilities, HEWS should be viewed as one tool amongst others for improving extreme heat preparedness, rather than a panacea. Adaptations to the growing threat of dangerous heat will include improved spatial planning and building design, hospital heat-health action plans, patient and staff awareness campaigns, and behaviour change [12,19,27,53]. Nonetheless, heat-health early warnings systems are among the most cost-effective solutions for resource-limited settings. Equal effort is needed to ensure that forecasts are effectively disseminated and framed

for different target audiences [54]. Hospitals are also well-placed to harness epidemiological data and information about inpatient volumes before, during, and after extreme heat events. Such health surveillance data can be used to advance beyond temperature forecasts, and progress to impact-orientated heat forecasting to enable prediction of heat-related admission surges. In short, improving preparedness for dangerous heat in Ghana, and elsewhere in resource-limited areas of tropical Africa, will involve integrating HEWS alongside a raft of other practical measures.

5. Conclusions

Ghana is already experiencing very high indoor temperatures that threaten the health and well-being of vulnerable people, such as pregnant women, neonates, and young children. This study tested and evaluated methods of forecasting ward-specific, maximum indoor temperatures 24 h ahead for hospitals in Accra and Tamale. Zero Order Forecast (ZOF) and linear regression models were trained using 2 years of indoor temperature data from low-cost sensors combined with outdoor temperatures from a weather prediction model (GFS). Forecast skill was assessed using r^2 , MAE, and TSS metrics, and found to be greatest for wards without air-conditioning or mechanical cooling systems, i.e., those that were naturally ventilated with a high degree of connection to the outdoors.

Inside naturally ventilated wards, the GFS-based model could explain up to 75 % of the variance in daily maximum temperature (Tx) with accuracies of ~ 1 °C at 24 h lead times. Such heat alerts can be used by hospital authorities to adjust staffing levels for expected surges in patient volumes, and for rescheduling of elective non-urgent outpatient

treatments to free up capacity. However, heatwave early warning systems (HEWS) should be integrated alongside other measures to adapt to rising indoor temperatures, such as improving hospital design, formulating heat health plans, and raising awareness of heat-related health issues.

Future priorities for research are to evaluate the relative skill of the ZOF and GFS-based indoor heat forecasts over longer lead-times than 24 h. There is also scope for incorporating extra predictor variables – like solar radiation and rainfall – in the statistical models to better capture abrupt changes in temperature, and to broaden the range of output metrics to cover humid heat.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Consuela Beauchamp-Davies: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Ben M. Roberts:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Robert L. Wilby:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Raymond Kasei:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Ebenezer F. Amankwaa:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Samuel Nii Ardey Codjoe:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Katherine V. Gough:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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